

Pharmacological treatment options for attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) in adults - current knowledge on efficacy and safety

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Abstract

Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is a childhood-onset neurodevelopmental disorder with a worldwide prevalence of approximately 5.9% in adolescents under the age of 18 and 2.5% in adults. Numerous randomised controlled trials show benefits of stimulant medication and atomoxetine. Despite the efficacy of ADHD medication, there are a few concerns about its influence on cardiovascular system.

The aim of our study is to review and summarize the information from numerous articles concerning the available ADHD medication, with focus on their efficacy, safety profiles and long-term adverse effects.

An extensive review of the current medical literature was recently performed which specifically focused on studies about current treatment options for ADHD. To this end, we insisted on using the tools of databases (such as PubMed and Google Scholar) to reach up-to-date and credible scientific publications. We reviewed articles concerning efficacy and safety of ADHD medications and their impact on general improvement in quality of life for patients presenting with ADHD.

There is a substantial evidence for the efficacy of psychostimulants and atomoxetine in reduction of core symptoms in children and adults. The risk for serious cardiovascular adverse events (sudden cardiac death, ventricular arrhythmia, stroke, myocardial infarction or a composite endpoint of stroke or myocardial infarction) associated with stimulants and atomoxetine prescribed for ADHD is extremely low and the benefits of ADHD treatment definitely outweigh the risks. Yet, an adequate assessment and great caution is recommended.

Key words

ADHD, medication, adverse effects, metylphenidate, atomoxetine

1. Introduction

Attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is among the most common neurodevelopmental disorders within psychiatric conditions, with a worldwide prevalence of approximately 5.9% in adolescents under the age of 18 and 2.5% in adults ^{[1][2]}.

Since publication of the first International Consensus Statement on ADHD ^[3] in 2002, the disorder started to be extensively investigated and clinically observed which led to significant outcomes. ADHD develops through the accumulation of numerous genetic and environmental risk factors, that have been emerging since fetal or early postnatal period, genetic abnormalities, severe brain trauma, neurobiological dysregulation or extreme deprivation in early childhood ^{[4][5]}. The diagnosis of ADHD relies on the thorough examination performed by a licensed clinician comprising of neuropsychological tests, rating scales, brain imaging and, if possible, a parent or caregiver observations concerning the patient's early childhood. ^[6]

Nowadays, plenty of misconceptions related to ADHD still occur in the public opinion, leading to stigmatization of affected people and delaying of the diagnosis and treatment process. ^[7] Moreover, adult population were excluded from crucial researches and clinical trials resulting in a knowledge gap on the pathophysiology and presentation of ADHD in older patients and the treatment methods, its efficacy, safety and possible long-term adverse effects. Pharmacological treatment of ADHD comprises of the most widely used psychostimulants – norepinephrine and dopamine reuptake inhibitors (methylphenidate hydrochloride, lisdexamfetamine dimesylate, dexamethylphenidate hydrochloride, etc.) or second-line medications – selective noradrenaline reuptake inhibitor (atomoxetine), alpha2 adrenergic receptor agonists (guanfacine, clonidine). Other unlicensed treatment options include antidepressants (bupropion hydrochloride, venlafaxine hydrochloride, desipramine hydrochloride, etc.) or antipsychotics (risperidone, aripiprazole, olanzapine, etc.).^[8]

2. Stimulants

Psychostimulants - methylphenidate (MPH) and amphetamine derivatives (AMP) - are among the most studied and promising pharmacological options in ADHD treatment. MPH has been reported to reduce the main symptoms of ADHD in approximately 70% of patients under the

age of 18. A meta-analysis of 6 clinical trials in adults with ADHD documented similar efficacy in adult population and estimated a robust effect size of 1.3 with optimized dosing of MPH (mean effect size, 0.9 at lower doses).^[10]

Psychostimulants inhibit dopamine and norepinephrine transporters and act as reuptake inhibitors increasing neurotransmission, especially in striatum and prefrontal cortex.^[9]

Using functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI), Vaidya et al. 2005 demonstrated selective effects of MPH in patients with ADHD compared with those without the disorder during the performance of 2 go/no-go tasks designed to evaluate motor inhibition. fMRI showed reduced striatal activation in ADHD patients versus controls during performance of the stimulus-controlled form of the task, however, the differences were absent after treatment with MPH.

Concerns about a broad range of possible adverse effects of long-term stimulant treatments have been highlighted by numerous health professionals. In 2009, after reviewing the available research evidence, the Committee for Medicinal Products for Humans Use (CHMP) noted a range of psychiatric adverse events, including aggression, mania, irritability, suicidality and suggested a key role of MPH in the development of serious psychiatric disorders. Moreover, clinical concerns include the potential cardiovascular adverse events.^[10]

3. Efficacy of methylphenidate

Methylphenidate is among the most widely studied medications used for ADHD treatment. Numerous clinical trials have been conducted in order to study short-term efficacy, as well as long-term safety of this psychostimulant. A randomized, double-blind, multicenter study of the methylphenidate transdermal system for the treatment of ADHD in adolescents conducted by Findling et al. 2010 included 217 participants and demonstrated greater reductions from baseline in ADHD-RS-IV total score. Subjects reported mild or moderate intensity adverse events, which included decreased appetite, headache, irritability and upper respiratory tract infection.^[11]

Another multisite controlled study of osmotic-release oral system (OROS) methylphenidate in the treatment of adolescents with attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder showed a significant reduction of ADHD symptoms. A group of 220 adolescents with a confirmed Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fourth Edition diagnosis of ADHD underwent dose titration to identify dosages of OROS methylphenidate that improved symptoms to specified criteria. Based on a Clinical Global Impression improvement subscale score of much or very much improved, 52% of subjects in the OROS methylphenidate group improved compared with 31% receiving placebo. Concluding, OROS methylphenidate administered once-daily reduced ADHD symptoms and was tolerated well using the maximum dose up to 72 mg/d. ^[12]

An extensive Cochrane systematic review prepared by [Storebø](#) et al. 2015 investigated the available data on the efficacy of methylphenidate and confirmed substantial improvement in general behaviour and quality of life among patients with the diagnosis of ADHD, however, the amount of 185 included trials were classified as being at high risk of bias. Aforementioned conclusions were criticised by experts in the field due to methodological choices of tools used for biased assessment. Those strict criteria labelled randomized clinical trials funded by government or independent agencies as biased if only one of the trials' authors had revealed a financial connection to any pharmaceutical company. ^[13]

A network meta-analysis performed by [Catalá-López](#) et al. 2017 including 190 randomized clinical trials of ADHD treatments (with a total of 26114 participants) confirmed that psychostimulants, with methylphenidate as a main representative, are the most efficacious treatment currently available for ADHD. The analysis considered not only pharmacological, but also non-pharmacological ways of treatment, including psychological therapy (behavioural, cognitive training and neurofeedback) and complementary and alternative medicine (dietary therapy, fatty acids, amino acids, minerals, herbal therapy, homeopathy, and physical activity). The efficacy of psychostimulants were associated in several adverse effects – anorexia, weight loss, insomnia, but there were no risk of serious adverse events observed. Moreover, this review found no differences in acceptability between psychostimulants and other pharmacological options. ^[14]

4. Atomoxetine

Atomoxetine (ATX) inhibits the norepinephrine transporter 1 (NET 1). It prevents the reuptake and therefore increases neurotransmission of norepinephrine in all regions of the brain and of dopamine specifically in the prefrontal cortex, where the dopamine transporters density is relatively small. In vitro studies suggest that in the prefrontal cortex, norepinephrine and dopamine are coreleased by noradrenergic neurons (Devoto et al 2001). This is consistent with preclinical studies demonstrating that atomoxetine increases dopamine in the rat prefrontal cortex but not the nucleus accumbens or striatum (Bymaster et al, in press), potentially accounting for its efficacy in ADHD as well as its lack of abuse potential (Heil et al 2002).^[15]

Atomoxetine's safety has been assessed in several clinical trials. In adults, reasons for discontinuing treatment included insomnia (1,1%), chest pain (0,7%), palpitations (0,7%) and urinary retention (0,7%). The average increases in blood pressure (approximately 3 mm Hg systolic/2 mm Hg diastolic) and pulse (around 8 beats per minute) in patients have been reported. Allergic reactions, such as urticaria, angioneurotic edema and rash have also been reported with atomoxetine use.^[16]

The tolerability profile of atomoxetine in adults differed somewhat from that seen in children, with more adverse events consistent with increased noradrenergic tone, including insomnia gastrointestinal and genitourinary symptoms, but overall tolerability appears to be satisfactory. Kratochvil et al. 2011 suggest that atomoxetine should be used cautiously in patients with hypertension or other risk factors. Atomoxetine appears to provide a promising therapy for adults with ADHD and, in contradiction to MPH, its lack of abuse potential may be an advantage for many patients.^[17]

5. Efficacy of atomoxetine

Atomoxetine is the main non-stimulant drug approved by the FDA for treating ADHD in children, adolescents and adults and provides a decent alternative, particularly when psychostimulants are contraindicated or not tolerated – when treatment with methylphenidate has been ineffective, in the presence of anxiety disorder and severe tics or when there is a risk

of misuse.^[18] Moreover, it may be considered as first-line treatment in substance abuse populations due to the lack of abuse potential, in contrast to methylphenidate, where a risk assessment for potential substance misuse and drug diversion is required when prescribing – that is not necessary for atomoxetine, which has no abuse potential.^[19] Atomoxetine might also be considered in some exceptional situations, when ADHD is comorbid with other psychiatric disorders. The Fifth Edition of Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-V) mentions the possibility of comorbid ADHD in autism, which provides an opportunity for the further study on both illnesses. The previous, Fourth Edition of DSM (DSM-IV) didn't allow to diagnose ADHD in the presence of autism, causing a great impairment of research in this area.^[20]

The response to treatment with atomoxetine in ADHD comorbid with Tourette syndrome or different tics disorders was satisfying for patients suffering from aforementioned conditions and neither intensified, nor worsened the accompanied disorder.^[21]

Perugi and Vannucchi in their literature review on the use of stimulants and atomoxetine in adults with comorbid ADHD and bipolar disorder postulate that atomoxetine used alongside mood stabilizers reduce the risk of precipitating mania, at least in non-acute patients.^[22]

Atomoxetine lacks effect in the striatum and requires at least 4 to 6 weeks to reach a full therapeutic potential; this needs to be counselled with patients and, optionally, their caregivers, so that patience in the process of treatment is exhibited. The optimal dose varies between individuals – clinical trials have investigated 0.5-, 1.2-, and 1.8-mg/kg doses and revealed that the higher the dose, the better ADHD symptom control, mood symptoms and family functioning, although lower doses are suggested to be used in the beginning of treatment to improve tolerability, followed by gradual weekly increase of the dose by 20 mg/day up to 100 mg/daily. Atomoxetine should be administered once daily in the morning or twice daily in the divided doses.^[23] Michelson et al. 2007 mention that atomoxetine is metabolized through cytochrome P-450 (CYP2D6) enzyme pathway, which is genetically polymorphic in humans. Approximately 7% of the population have mutations or deletions in the genes codifying this enzymatic group and as a consequence – this group of patients would be poor metabolizers of atomoxetine; that may result in reduced tolerance and increased rate of side effects.^[24]

Atomoxetine is in general well-tolerated with side effects reported to be less severe than in case of stimulants. There is no need to monitor liver function, however, if hepatic impairment is observed, both initial and target doses should be reduced. Despite its rather safe profile, atomoxetine ought not to be administered in patients with cardiomyopathy, uncontrolled hypertension, cardiac arrhythmias and structural cardiac abnormalities.^[25]

6. Safety and cardiovascular concerns of the ADHD treatment

In the light of many controversies arousing around the increase in the number of patients being diagnosed with ADHD, the more common use of methylphenidate and other amphetamine derivatives and their influence on the cardiovascular system, the topic of methylphenidate's adverse effects should also be taken into consideration. [26]

One of the largest retrospective, population-based cohort studies concerning ADHD medications and risk of serious cardiovascular events in young and middle-aged adults, conducted by Habel et al., included a total of 443,198 adults of whom 150,359 had dispensed prescriptions for methylphenidate, atomoxetine or amphetamine at baseline. No evidence of an increased risk of myocardial infarction (MI), sudden cardiac death or stroke was found, associated with current use compared with nonuse (adjusted rate ratio [RR]: 0.83, 95% CI 0.72, 0.96) or remote use (adjusted RR: 1.03), 95% CI 0.86, 1.24) of ADHD medications. [27]

Another nonrandomized cohort study aimed to determine whether use of methylphenidate in adults is associated with elevated rates of serious cardiovascular events (sudden cardiac death, ventricular arrhythmias, stroke, myocardial infarction or a composite endpoint of stroke or myocardial infarction), compared with rates in nonusers, conducted by Shelleman et al., matched a total of 43,999 new methylphenidate adult users (18 years of age or older) with 175,955 nonusers from a five-state Medicaid database covering 1999-2003 and a commercial insurance database, covering the period 2001-2006 were included in this study. Whereas, there was no statistically significant difference in risk was found for stroke, myocardial infarction and a combined endpoint of stroke or myocardial infarction, the increased risk of sudden cardiac death or ventricular arrhythmia among methylphenidate users was proven (adjusted hazard ratio: 1.84, 95% CI 1.33, 2.55). Nevertheless, the dosage was inversely associated with risk and authors concluded that the lack of a dose-response relationship between methylphenidate use and risk of sudden death or ventricular arrhythmia suggest that this association may not be a casual one. [28]

Holick et al's population-based cohort study conducted to estimate the association between atomoxetine and cerebrovascular accident (CVA) and transient ischemic attack (TIA) in adults, compared use of atomoxetine (a non-stimulant associated with increases in blood pressure; n = 21,606) to use of stimulant ADHD medications (n = 21,606). Use of atomoxetine was not

associated with a greater risk of stroke of transient ischemic attack (TIA), in comparison with stimulant ADHD medications. Secondary analysis, where atomoxetine and stimulant users were matched to a general population cohort (n = 42,993) had a significantly increased risk of transient ischemic attack (TIA), but not stroke. [29]

7. Conclusion

Attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is a chronic condition which requires ongoing pharmacological treatment and monitoring. Among treatment options, several medications can be distinguished - most widely used psychostimulants – norepinephrine and dopamine reuptake inhibitors (methylphenidate hydrochloride, lisdexamfetamine dimesylate, dexamethylphenidate hydrochloride, etc.) or second-line medications, like a selective noradrenaline reuptake inhibitor (atomoxetine). Long-standing clinical experience headlines that therapeutic interventions, special education and counselling of the patients and their caregivers is necessary to complete the drug therapy with most long-term positive effects. Psychostimulants are highly effective in comparison with other psychiatric medication while non-stimulants, supposed to be less effective, should be considered in certain situations, including substance abuse disorder, comorbidity of ADHD with other psychiatric disorders – bipolar disorder, autism or Tourette syndrome. The selection of treatment should be based on shared decision-making process between the physician and his or her patient, thorough examination and medical history. An individual assessment of the response to treatment and manifestation of adverse effects should be routinely conducted.

In spite of existing controversy, risk for serious cardiovascular adverse events (sudden cardiac death, ventricular arrhythmias, stroke, myocardial infarction or a composite endpoint of stroke or myocardial infarction) associated with prescribed ADHD medications is low and the potential benefits of treating individual patients, after a thorough assessment and potential inclusion of a medication-free interval outweighs the risk. [30]

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